

This is an original manuscript of an article published by Taylor & Francis in Rethinking History on 01 September 2025, available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642529.2025.2545028>

Internationalism as Lived Experience: Some critical reflections

The question of the lived experience has been on the agenda of historians of internationalism for more than a decade. However, little effort has been made to engage with the new history of experiences literature. This conceptual/experimental article considers the potentials this literature holds for studying the history of internationalism. It does so by discussing three distinct, but interconnected, points: the importance of emotions and the senses, the need to reconsider the concept of agency and the significance of collective experiences.

Keywords: lived experience; internationalism; emotions, senses, agency and collective experiences

Introduction

In 2021, Jessica Reinisch and David Brydan made a pronounced case for ‘internationalism as lived experience’ in their edited volume, *Internationalists in European History*. Drawing on studies that had set out to challenge ‘familiar chronologies and geographies of internationalism’, the contributors to the volume ‘restore[d] a sense of lived experience of internationalism’ by exploring how international organisations and institutions ‘affected and were shaped by the people involved with their work’ whether as ‘agents’ or ‘targets’ (7). While Reinisch and Brydan’s volume was the first to make a case for lived experiences, it was far from the only study that had considered lived experiences. The question of the lived experience informs Whitney Walton’s examination of internationalism, national identities and study abroad programmes between France and the United States (2009); Jonah Steinberg’s study of Isma’ili modern (2011); Ali Reza’s exploration of communist internationalism in colonial India (2020); and Patricia Owens and Katharina Rietzler’s

history of women's international thought (2021). In other words, lived experiences have been on the agenda of historians of internationalism for more than ten years. Despite this more-than-a-decade long preoccupation with lived experiences, attempts are yet to be made to engage with the new history of experiences literature, and its underlying argument for emotions and the senses as integral parts of experiences, critique of agency and discussion of collective experiences.

This experimental/conceptual article seeks to discuss the potentials that the new history of experiences holds for studying the history of internationalism. At this important moment in the writing of the history of experiences, when it is rapidly expanding (see HEX Digital Handbook of the History of Experience), understanding these potentials is crucial. Far from arguing for departing from existing studies on internationalism as lived experience, this article's goal is to see these studies from the vantage point of the new history of experiences. In other words, the article considers the new history of experiences as an 'other' place (Rendell, 2013) – that is, another discipline and way of doing – from where, and by operating at the edge of which, historians of internationalism can explore their position and consider the differences it makes to what they can know. Architectural historian and critic, Jane Rendell, describes this process of operating between and at the edge of disciplines as being 'horizontal' rather than 'vertical', meaning that it examines 'the points where disciplines fall apart and come together' (129). As she explains, this process '*is difficult*'; it is laden with uncertainty and unpredictability that can result in fragile forms of knowledge, yet it *is* transformative. Taking Rendell's argument into consideration, this article surrenders the safety of competence in favour of the dangers of uncertainty and the certainty of attachment in favour of the fear of detachment (Solnit, 2014, 15) to offer not concrete forms of knowledge but transformative forms of analysis.

In the following, I first provide a short overview of scholarship in the history of internationalism, digging deeper into interventions of discussions concerning lived experiences. I then consider these interventions from the vantage point of the new history of experiences literature. To do so, I explain the main claims and promises of this literature. Subsequently, based on these claims and promises, I put forward three distinct, but interrelated, arguments. These arguments highlight how putting emotions and the senses at the centre of historiographical practices in the history of internationalism helps both rethink the concept of agency and contemplate collective experiences. My hope is that historians of internationalism can benefit from, and build on, these arguments in their ongoing efforts to write decentred histories.

History of internationalism

Scholarship on the history of internationalism has been rapidly expanding since the 1990s. Initially, perspectives of Western, and often Anglo-American, actors and members of organisations such as the United Nations (UN) and the World Health Organisation (WHO) were primary lenses for exploration (Clavin, 2005; Weindling, 1995). While studying the activities of international organisations still remains an important topic, more recent efforts have tried to broaden the perspective in diverse ways. These efforts, and their underlying concerns, questions and claims, have not of course gone uncontested and been welcomed differently across disciplines, but they have made clear the diversity and multiplicity of worldviews, priorities and orders at work. A group of scholars has introduced philanthropies and other private sectors, nongovernmental organisations (NGOs) and in-country efforts to the narrative (Nuijsink and Bonzanigo, 2023; O’Sullivan, 2021; Nunan, 2015; Birn, 2014; 2006); another has turned the lens to socialist and fascists variations of internationalism (Vargha, 2023;

Roth-Ey, 2023; Donert and Moll-Murata, 2022; Erofeev and Stanek, 2021; Stanek, 2020; Imlay, 2017); and yet another has examined south-south patterns of cooperation and non-aligned movement as alternative circuits of international exchange (Birn and Necochea López, 2020; Lewis and Stolte, 2019; Amrith, 2017, 2006; Lee, 2010).

Alongside these studies, there has been works on Black internationalists, who forged pan-African and anti-colonial networks (Milford, 2022; Umoren, 2018; Adi, 2018), and Muslim internationalists, whose activities were rooted in adopted pre-modern ideas and values (Mukherjee, 2017; Bennison, 2012; Clarence-Smith, 2012). Importantly, the boundaries of these different versions of internationalism were not always clear cut; depending on time and context, ideas could overlap, present themselves as diverse options and shape in interaction with one another (Milford, 2022; Klaus Patel, 2021, Reza, 2020).

Collectively, these studies pose questions of who counts as internationalists and hence how internationalism could or could not have been practised. By beginning with these questions, rather than jumping into analysis with a ready-made definition, they help see dynamics of gender and race at work as well as other forms of power relations, embedded in normative definitions and categories that conceal alternative ideas, practices and movements. In doing so, they argue against standard periodisation, a mere focus on international organisations and their Anglo-American liberal actors and members, interstate and nation-state relations and ‘urban hubs’ like London, Paris, Brussels or New York, and thus any notions of ‘real’ or ‘pure’ forms of internationalism (also see Lewis, 2023; Zarakol, 2022, 2021). The history of internationalism, as these studies demonstrate, is complex, multifaceted and multcentred. Internationalisms at times emerged in urban and rural areas of countries such as China, India and Tanzania and for the Global South by people who had never travelled to Europe (Brazelton, 2022;

Sivasundaram, 2021; Hunter, 2015). These versions of internationalism were not always long-term and far-reaching, nor were they always products of ‘willing’ agents, nor were they always utopian and radical. Rather they were sometimes channelled by ‘reluctant’ actors, some of whom were prejudiced, and were short-term and limited (Tudor, 2023; Antic, Conterio and Vargha, 2016; Burton, 2016). Far from discounting developments in Europe and North America, these studies show how scholars can account for them without favouring them over ideas and worldviews that originated, shaped by and circulated in the Global South. Even if we take the meaning of internationalism as a given and a product of liberal international discourse, we cannot deny that liberal internationalism neither outlived nor completely overshadowed other forms of world order, and thus cannot be understood in vacuum.

Internationalism as lived experience is a part and parcel of this shift toward writing more decentred and counter-hegemonic histories of internationalism. Characterised by phrases such as ‘listening to’ (Reza, 2020, 8-14) and ‘theorising with’ (Shilliam, 2021, 158-78), it seeks to challenge the very understanding of international thought and practice by turning the lens not only to the ‘experts’ on the ground (Piana, 2016), but also to ‘disembodied’ and ‘isolated’ voices. It explores their interactions with international organisations and looks at how internationalisms were experienced by them and how those experiences, charged with ‘conflicts’ and ‘tensions’, transformed international organisations and institutions. In doing so, it questions the assumed ‘unity’ of international organisations and institutions, while challenging fixed definitions, thus revealing a more fractured and ambiguous picture.

What does the new history of experience have to offer?

What is the new history of experience? In the words of Rob Boddice and Mark Smith, it

is the study of ‘the lived, meaningful reality of historical actors, whether as subjective or collective reality, and incorporating all the features of past perception in their own terms, be they sensory, emotional, cognitive, supernatural or whatever’ (Boddice and Smith, 2020, 17). We can take three essential interconnected points from this explanation. The first point is the reinstatement of emotions and the senses, but neither as universal and constant, nor as mere effect of historical circumstances; emotions and the senses have history and make history (For example, see Boddice, 2023, 2019; Matt and Stearns, 2014; Howes and Classen, 2014; Frevert, 2011; Smith, 2007; Classen, 1993). The new history of experiences, thus, underscores Joan Scott’s (1991) warning against treating the ‘evidence of experience’ as something ‘foundational’, ‘irreducible’, ‘concrete’ or ‘natural’, while criticising her overemphasise on ‘discourse as the root of everything’ and hence her abandonment of the body, feelings and the senses (Boddice and Smith, 2021, 19).

The second point brings emotions and the senses into an intertwined complex relationship. Arguing that ‘historical concepts of experience often bear little resemblance to “emotion” or “sense”, but rather combine affective and cognitive categories in more general concept of feeling’ (Boddice and Smith, 2020, 9), it strives for the study of experience as a ‘construction of brain-body-world dynamics’ (Boddice, 2023). To this end, it argues against any prior assumption about agency as an autonomous category or ‘an objective existence outside of human situated biology’ (Boddice and Smith, 2020, 52). The bottom line is if we accept that the ‘politics of exclusion’ leaves imprints on the body-mind, then it influences and delimits ‘the ways in which situated biology is permitted to engage’ with the world (51). This process is dynamic rather than directional. That is, any uncritical engagement with the concept of agency risks softening the impact of domination (Brownlie and Kelm, 1994). The

contention is that, since there is no such a thing as ‘an authentic, unmediated [and unchanging] interiority’ (Alexander, Olsen, Vallgård, 2023), the concept of agency should be framed as a question, rather than the ‘defining contribution’ of an exploration (Thomas, 2016; Johnson, 2003, 114). Being agentic is only one experience, one way of being, among others. Moreover, instead of being uniform, agency takes on various forms and is subject to change over time (Olsen, et. al., 2024).

The third point rejects any universalising notion of human formation, including subjectivity. Emphasising its situatedness, rather than rejecting its importance, the new history of experiences asks how we can theorise with and about and analyse other situated types of formation, such as collective experience, incorporating collective agency (Boddice and Hitzer, 2022, 6). It goes beyond assuming that simply being a member of a community, a group or a team accounts for having a collective experience to ask how and under what circumstances people are drawn together and ‘united in experience’. It draws important distinctions between ‘common’ experiences on the one hand and ‘shared’ experiences on the other, with the former referring to experiencing the same event, occurrence or crisis, either over time or across space, while the latter referring to the recognition of the ‘sameness’ by an aggregate of people (Kivimäki, Malinen and Vuolanto, 2023; Boddice and Hitzer, 2022, 7).

Through these three points, the new history of experiences suggests ‘the possibility of substantial historiographical revision’ (Boddice and Hitzer, 2022, 5). This suggested revision is neither top-down nor bottom-up; it focuses on the dynamic of historical encounters as broadly conceived, meaning that it pays attention to the body-mind-world that led to and went on after a specific moment of encounter (Boddice and Hitzer, 2022, 4; Kivimäki, Suodenjoki and Vahtikari, 2021). Here it is important to note that expectations, desires and memories, and their various social, cultural and political

impulses, should be taken seriously but without being treated as either distinct from experiences (Reza, 2020, 16) or as being prior to them (Franke, 2022). The key is to consider how they form experiences while being plastic and having lives of their own. This consideration entails placing expectations, desires and memories in context (Parhi, 2022), while avoiding the temptation to draw on one's own expectations, desires and memories as 'source[s] of knowledge' (Lee, 2020).

To demonstrate the potentials the new history of experiences holds for studying the history of internationalism, the remainder of the article considers these three interconnected points, discussing each in turn.

Emotions and the Senses

Existing studies on internationalism as lived experience rarely consider emotions and the senses. It is out of the scope of this article to discuss why this lack of consideration has been the case. Whatever the reasons may be – persistent assumptions that link rationality with sovereignty (Matt and Stearns, 2014) or 'frequent ignorance toward affect' in classical social and cultural theory (Reckwitz, 2012, 242) – important are how historians of internationalism can meaningfully engage with emotions and the senses and write about them. Noting that every cross-cultural encounter has an affective-cognitive structuration (Gammerl, Nielsen and Pernau, 2019; Reckwitz, 2012) may be one way to introduce emotions and the senses into the discussion. In fact, existing and emerging works on friendship, gift-giving and internationalism (Moore, 2021; Stanek, 2022; Applebaum, 2019) have already taken some steps in this direction. Discussing not only friendship, but also 'trust' and 'love', Ilaria Scaglia has even gone further to show that emotions 'became a fundamental feature of internationalism' starting from the nineteenth century (2020, 2). But a more fruitful approach, one that would strive to put

emotions and the senses at the centre of the historiography of internationalism, would inquire into their histories. In doing so, it would recognise our modern assumptions about emotion/cognition and head/heart binaries, being prepared all the while to let go of them (for examples of this having been done in other fields, see Boddice, 2016; Classen, 2012; Alberti, 2009).

One study that considers emotions is Jonah Steinberg's *Isma'ili Modern*, which explore the development of Isma'ili Muslims (followers of His Highness the Aga Khan IV) global structure in the twentieth first century. Steinberg states that 'he writes ... in dialogue with [Isma'ili subjects] ... that [he has] tried to be respectful of their words, their feelings, and their realities' (2011, 107). But nowhere in his otherwise revealing study does he construct the situated meanings of feelings and realities – encompassing the non-verbal, such as posture and expression. His discussion of *didār* is a case in point. Steinberg states that *didār* 'translates loosely from Persian as "audience" (as with king) or "vision"' (102). This loose translation is correct. Nevertheless, pre- and early modern Islamic-Arabic linguistic traditions made important distinctions between 'vision' and 'seeing'. While distinct, they were intertwined 'in meaning and conceptual scope', and together with looking, they defined the nature of visual perception as a sensory, imaginative, cognitive and reflective act (Akkach, 2022, 13-14). Steinberg's examination of *didār* disregards its semantic complexities, does not chart them over time and is unfaithful to Isma'ili community situated alternative interpretations (Boddice and Smith, 2020, 9-15 and 47-9; Boddice, 2019; Boquet and Nagy, 2018). All members of the Isma'ili Muslim community – a globally and culturally diverse community – have not been practising and experiencing *didār* uniformly, not least because the way *didār* is operationalised and enforced has been changing over time and space.

What the situated understating of *didār* could have added to the discussion.

Steinberg refers to *didār* in his examination of ‘devotional practices’ and their centrality ‘to the cohesion and integrity of the Isma‘ili transnational community’ (101) with the purpose of revealing the ‘agency’ of Isma‘ilis and hence demonstrating how there could be ‘multiple Isma‘ili globalizations’ (85). He emphasises that while *didār* is key to the formation of a transnational Isma‘ili sense of commonality and shared experience’ (102), it ‘appears to exist outside the institutional infrastructure’. While he notes that there can be ‘contestation’, he recognises *didār* as ‘a peak experience’ and ‘a dream to be attained’ for ‘many Isma‘ilis’ (102). The situated meanings of *didār* would have assisted in better understanding of how it felt ‘to be there, then’ (Boddice, 2019, 9) according to the terms of Isma‘ilis. This understanding could have helped Steinberg explore the scale, scope and form of Isma‘ilis’ agency, rather than simply claiming they have agency. He could have also explored how multiple grasps of *didār* united and divided Isma‘ilis, traced these unions and divisions over time and examined their influence on the scale and scope of Isma‘ilis’ agency. I will return to these points in the following sections. But, in short, the situated meaning of *didār* would have brought to light extra layers of complexity. Far from revealing either a united or fractured Isma‘ili globalisation, it would have shown how, depending on time and context, the nature of Isma‘ili globalisation has changed.

Agency

Like Steinberg’s study, scholarship on internationalism as lived experience began their examination with the proposition that the so-called targets of internationalism – be they users, pupils, students and craftsmen, to name but a few types of people – had agency. While they discuss issues such as the politics of access, material constraints (such as

passport restrictions), language barriers and misunderstandings and failures of communication, their purpose is to show how people navigated these limitations, inequalities and difficulties, and exercised agency. These studies often employ a bottom-up approach; they search for lost documents, incorporate oral history and read between lines of historical materials to recover silenced or forgotten voices to show how everyone, regardless of constraints, played a role. Put differently, agency, defined by modern understanding of the self and rational choices (Maynes, 2008), is the argument or the defining contribution of this scholarship. Thus, it appears that diverse groups of people regardless of their background and identity – be they schoolchildren in multilingual Penang of the 1920s (Lewis, 2018, 196-201), ‘the seemingly ordinary subjects who inhabited’ communism and communist thought in India (Reza, 2020, 8), activists and intellectuals, who carried discourses of Afro-Asian solidarity, internationalism and peace before and beyond the Bandung conference (Lewis and Stolte, 2019) or Mongolian people during the construction of Cold War Mongolia (Erofeev and Stanek, 2021) – had equal or comparable agency. We are left with a history where multidirectional exchanges and interactions invariably resulted in a ‘flattened world’ (Nasr and Volait, 2003), even though recent works on global disconnection have been arguing the contrary (Wenzlhuemer, 2022; 2020, Biedermann, 2021).

The questions of which schoolchildren, ordinary subjects, activists and intellectuals and so on understood their ‘experiences as formative for their sense of identity and belonging’, to what extent and for how long have remained largely unexplored (Kivimäki, Suodenjoki and Vahtikari, 2021, 14). In other words, these narratives set up a false dichotomy: either people have individual agency or else they simply ‘exist’ as passive bystanders. Little is said about various notions of the self (Liu,

1997), including the collective self. The lifeworld and experiences of all those who never simply cared enough to engage, question or change is also assumed as unworthy of consideration. Moreover, if someone stopped to engage, resist, interact or converse, they simply ceased to exist. In other words, no room is left for a range of choices, expressions, responses, actions or, in short, experiences (Olsen, et. al., 2024; Boddice and Smith, 2020), diverse ways of being and becoming and changes over time (Olsen, et. al., 2024).

Following Fanny H. Brotons (2017), Rob Boddice and Mark Smith suggest constructing the ‘context of possibilities’ (2020, 50) to avoid the ‘agency trap’ (Gleason, 2016). While Su Lin Lewis and Carolien Stolte (2022) and Gary Wilder (2015) have emphasised the importance of inquiring into the range of (unrealised) possibilities, ‘anti-imperialist agendas’ and ‘alternative forms of life’ in world making after empire, they have not gone so far as to redefine the concept of agency. What is novel about the context of possibilities when considered with reference to the history of internationalism is not just its openness to different interpretations of internationalism, but also its willingness to allow internationalism to exist as just one possibility. The focus of examination shifts in this way from an acknowledgment of agency as a conclusion to a study of the form, scale and scope of the activities of people.

For example, consider studies that contemplate international conferences, competitions (Legg, Heffernan, Hodder and Thorpe, 2021; Nuijsink, 2021) or design projects (Bolca, 2023; Seng and Chang, 2022; Erofeev and Stanek, 2021; Fenk, Lee and Motylińska, 2020). Some scholars have developed the concept of ‘cross-cultural contact zones’ (Avermaete and Nuijsink, 2021) to show how these meetings and projects facilitated transculturation (Juneja, 2024) or multicultural exchanges of knowledge. Considering the exclusive nature of these meetings and projects (Gold, 2013), other

scholars have discussed the importance of going beyond these meetings and projects to widen their historiographical treatment by including a broader spectrum of people and sites of interaction and conversation (such as journeys, private initiatives, personal communication, etc) (Lewis and Stolte, 2019; Pinia, 2016). The context of possibilities helps expand on and complicate these arguments. It goes beyond transculturation by questioning not only the assumption that communication was probable (Nehring, 2005, 561-2) but also the assumption that there was an individual self-determination on the part of each person to change, contribute and re-order international structures. Instead, it situates what people said and done in the context of what they could have known about international exchanges, context-specific debates, political and social exigencies and so on (Boddice and Smith, 2020, 50). It explores means and manners of communication available to them, including non-verbal communication techniques, as well as their preceding experiences (Gammerl, Nielsen and Pernau, 2019). Furthermore, the context of possibilities regards diverse categories of people, and hence ways of being, including those who exercised agency as a collective or accepted and followed rules and regulations. Thus, it helps examining, or at least speculating about, each person's own definition and interpretation of their activities.

Collective experiences

As already mentioned, historians of internationalism have not endeavoured to theorise (with) different ways of life as much as they have tried to recognise them. This has particularly been the case as regards collective experiences. Studies that discuss the impact of professional and intimate ties (Bond, 2023; Specter, 2023; Lewis and Stolte, 2022), explore (multilateral) collaboration (Kubo, 2022; Erofeev and Stanek, 2021; Beyer, 2019) and stress the importance of exploring intersections and interactions

among diverse internationalisms on the ground (Patel, 2021) allude to collective experiences. But like Steinberg's, these studies assume the existence of a collective experience with the aim of recovering agency. Thus, they fail to theorise adequately (with) collective experiences. Experiencing the same thing as a part of a group or a community does not unequivocally lead to a feeling of collective experience. The first question to ask before one can have any hope of recovering collective experiences is: How does experiencing the same thing as individuals lead to a feeling of collective experience? This question entails asking about circumstances that facilitated the formation of a collective at a given time and place.

Ville Kivimäki, Antti Malinen and Ville Vuolanto have developed the theoretical concept of 'communities of experience' to examine collective experiences (2023). Far from arguing that communities of experience could be recognised by merely studying norms and practices (Rosenwein, 2006; 2002), they argue for the 'conscious existence' of a community of experience for the historical actors. Thus, their argument turns away from assuming sameness in experiences to focus on the perception of the sameness of experience by historical people. This perception could either be imaginary or 'discussed, processed or debated' among them.

If we consider the concept of communities of experience, it becomes clearer why the practice of *didār*, discussed earlier, does not unite all Isma'ilis across time and space. It links those who recognise a sameness in their understanding and experience of *didār*. This recognition is not timeless and can change over time, because a community of experience is unstable. It is important to identify these different unions because their formation excludes some Isma'ilis, influencing the scale and scope of their agency. In other words, the practice of *didār* can both facilitate and impede agency. The same can be said for collaboration and multicultural exchanges. The concept of community of

experience helps contemplate not only why collaboration and multicultural exchanges could involve tension and be uneven (Erofeev and Stanek, 2021) but also how they could hinder agency. While studies have shown that collaboration could mean different things from division of labour to sharing of input or a variation of both (Kubo, 2022, 18), they have not gone so far to emphasise the importance of considering every involved person different interpretation of collaboration. These differences could influence the nature of their interactions. These studies have also failed to take into account situations where collaboration, as a concept, may not have been available to every involved person. Collaboration could have limited the agency of these people by impeding the development of a feeling of collective experience. The analytical implication is that understanding collective experiences requires a step-by-step examination: appreciating experiences of each person on their terms, recognising sameness in their experiences, before making any claims about their involvement and agency.

Conclusions

In their efforts to write decentred histories of internationalism, historians of internationalism have turned to lived experiences over the last decade or so but without engaging with the new history of experiences literature. This literature emphasises the importance of emotions and the senses, criticises the notion of agency and rejects any universalising notion of human formation. This article considered each of these points in turn and discussed the potentials they hold for studying the history of internationalism. Considering the situated meanings of emotions and the senses means understanding people's experiences on their terms. This understanding results in a more nuanced evaluation of people's choices, activities and ways of being because recovering

agency is no longer the defining contribution of a study nor is tracing different interpretations of internationalism. Being prepared to let internationalism exist as one possibility is a necessity if one aims to write about (and with) lived experiences.

Acknowledgements, to be added after the peer review.

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